

DESTRUCTION AS A WHOLE PHENOMENON

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There are certain categories of people in society who are always trying to create something, and innovate, and some, on the contrary, strive to destroy the existing thing or situation. People of the second type can harm not only others but also themselves. In the field of social sciences, including psychology, this concept is called destructive, that is, destructive or destructive behavior. The concept of destruction refers to a person's use of certain actions to cause physical or moral damage to himself or others. Destructiveness causes irreparable harm to a person, physical self-consciousness, inability to think positively and deal with other people, and degradation of the person, i.e. internal spiritual disorder, and inability to create something new or something.

Destruction can be aimed at one's self, other people, and the whole world. In the first case, a person presents a danger to himself, and in the second case, he poses a danger to the surrounding people and the environment. Usually, a destructive person is very lonely. In all cases, the analysis and prevention of destructive behavior requires a professional approach and correction from a psychotherapist.¹

So what does the concept of "destruction" mean? Translated from Latin, "destructio" means "destruction". In a word, it is an antonym of the word "construction" (Latin "constructio" - to build, to build). The term "destructive behavior" is often used to refer to children and adolescents, but this concept is common to all people, regardless of age.

Destructive behavior is manifested at a turning point or in a critical period of a person's life as a defense against an aggressor, a person, or a source of a negative situation, as a response (reaction) to a situation, or as an open expression of self-hatred. The behavior of a destructive person surprises the surrounding people and leads to misunderstanding. However, few people are confused about the real reasons for this destructive activity.

Scientific problems related to destructive human behavior have been the object of research for a long time, even before the emergence of psychology as an independent discipline.

The concept of destructive behavior as human behavior contrary to the norms of human

society was developed by the great thinkers of antiquity, Plato, Aristotle, Hippocrates, and others. A philosophical understanding of the category of destruction or destructive behavior allowed him to formulate several approaches.

First of all, it is necessary to distinguish the moral aspects of destructive behavior studied within the philosophical schools of Stoics and Epicureans (IV century BC). Destructive behavior was interpreted as a deviation from the ideal of a person who harmoniously combines "naturalness and emotionality". The second direction - Ibn Sina, Averroes, and Galen were scientists who studied destructive behavior within the framework of natural-scientific knowledge. Their conclusions made it possible to form assumptions about the dependence of the individual mind on the cultural forms of social life, on the biological condition as the basis of the human mental state, and the dependence of temperament as a formal dynamic structure of the organization of mental life. The study of psychopathology and mental illness continued in the Middle Ages. The scientists of that time were focused on the interrelationship of somatic and mental diseases and their manifestation. In particular, famous religious scholars P. Abeyar and F. Aquinas' works are devoted to the causes of the deviant behavior of a person.

Also, the various forms of destructive behavior were described by prominent scientists of the Renaissance B. Telezio, X. Huarte, K. as a representative of natural sciences during the Enlightenment period. Helvetsiy, P. Holbach, J. Locke, and others have studied. At the same time, the moral foundations of destructive behavior L. Feuerbach, G. Hegel, I. Formed by philosophers such as Kant.

In the second half of the XIX century, within the framework of anthropology, destructive behavior was defined by E. Rothacker, A. Gaen, and M. Shellers. In the current period, it is emphasized that there is no direct objective connection between the destructive behavior of the person and the constitutional-biological characteristics. At the same time, individual-typological characteristics of a person (temperament or character traits) serve as formal dynamic conditions.²

Destructive behavior (behavior) is a verbal or practical manifestation of the internal activity of a person, the result of which is the destruction of something. As a rule, destructive behavior is aimed at communication between people, mutual relations, material objects, and a person's own physical or emotional state. Simply put, when a person's inner world is threatened by something, he destroys everything around him: he treats people or animals rudely, destroys property or equipment, commits acts of violence, etc. Often, destructive behavior is also called deviant behavior. This is true in essence because destructive behavior is considered regressive, a

negative form of the phenomenon of deviance.

When this behavior is approached from the point of view of medical, psychological, and social rules and opinions, it is considered a deviation from a certain limit, which ultimately leads to a decrease in the quality of human life, a cognitive disorder in the perception of events, as well as emotional disorders and deviations, and a decrease in human self-esteem. will come The consequences of destructive behavior can be different: from a person's "separation" from society to complete alienation.

Often, this behavior is characteristic of teenagers, because they go through periods of sharp changes in their lives, changes characteristic of the age of transition occur in the psyche; they face initial problems in society, that is, as a result of not understanding them by the older generation, destructive changes occur in the individual, which is reflected in destructive or destructive behavior.

Destructive behavior is manifested in the following:

- in the destructive change of character and client;
- in the formation of false self-evaluation;
- violation of personal motives and needs;
- not being able to control their behavior;
- in the violation of interaction with people.

A person who shows fear, impatience, and aggression towards reality, that is, the environment, people, animals, and material things, violates the moral norms and rules accepted by society, which means that he is a destructive person.

In psychology, this behavior is considered an interaction between a stimulus (stimulus) and a response (reaction) to it, and the response itself can be external or internal. The external reaction is manifested in actions, behavior, and the process of communication, that is, when it comes to destructive reactions, it is cruelty to animals, vandalism, terrorist attacks, etc.

The internal reaction is reflected in the process of emotional perception, and motivation, that is, in the reason that calls for an action, in cognitive processing. Also, destructive behavior can be directed at the "inner" side of the subject. Addiction to alcohol and drugs, as well as suicide, are manifestations of destruction. In any situation, the internal destructive thought always finds its way to the external environment and is manifested in human behavior.

In short, the destructive pattern of behavior always causes a negative reaction in people, it harms not only the environment but also the person who shows it. This situation is a specific response to the situation, and it is the result of a person's inability to control his mental and

emotional side and wrong adaptation to society.³

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